

LAKBAY-DIWA
Publishing

e-ISSN 3082-4397
p-ISSN 3082-5741

Volume I Issue VI

ECHOES *of* EXPRESSION

A Creative Folio

OCTOBER 2025
MONTHLY ISSUE
NATIONAL

NATIONAL BOOK PUBLISHER IN THE PHILIPPINES
DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937
TIN 492-741-614
lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com
Butuan City, Philippines
+639543906965

Volume I Issue VI

ECHOES of EXPRESSION

A Creative Folio

Echoes of Expression

A Creative Folio

Volume I, Issue VI (October 2025), National Circulation

ISSN (Online) 3082-4397 ISSN (Print) 3082-5741

Published Online at www.lakbaydiwapublishing.com

Publisher: Lakbay-Diwa Publishing

DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937 / TIN 492-741-614

lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com

Butuan City, Philippines

+639543906965

MARLITA P. NIERRAS, MPM

Assistant Professor I, School of Technology and Computer Studies

Biliran Province State University – Main Campus

Naval, Biliran Province, Region VIII, Philippines

[DOI 10.5281/zenodo.17340600](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17340600)

Gender-Inclusive Education in the Philippine Curriculum

(A Theoretical Essay)

Gender equality serves a foundation of autonomous and gender-responsive education. In the Philippine perspective, incorporating gender equity framework in the Philippine higher education curriculum signifies both moral and legal obligation. This integration is based on Republic Act No. 9710 or also known as Magna Carta of Women and Commission of Higher Education (CHED) Memorandum Order No. 1, Series of 2015. These legal bases require Philippine higher education institutions (HEIs) to institutionalize gender sensitivity and equality in instruction, research services, and governance. However, many HEIs remain to treat gender education as additional topic rather than critical pedagogical framework. This theoretical essay explores that gender-inclusive education must exceed symbolic inclusion and instead be considered as a theoretical and pedagogical shift toward equality and fairness.

Theoretical Foundations of Gender-Inclusive Education

Gender-inclusive education portrays on the different theories such as the feminist theory, gender mainstreaming, and critical pedagogy which serve as a foundational framework. According to Hooks (1994) feminist theory argues the patriarchal structure that imitate marginalization in education and advocates for the inclusion of underrepresented voices. As defined by the United Nations (1997), gender mainstreaming needs to incorporate gender perspectives in all areas of policy, planning, and implementation. In the education perspective, it calls for academic curriculum restructure that indicates plurality of gender narratives rather than upholding binary gender norms.

Critical pedagogy of Paulo Freire (1970) supplements this approach through putting education as a transformative learning practice. It invites educators and learners to challenge social hierarchies and participate in developmental learning process. In the Philippine context, this entails critically confronting deeply embedded cultural norms that prefer male dominance, uphold heteronormative values, and maintain hierarchical gender relations that disregard women and gender-diverse individuals.

Gender Mainstreaming in Philippine Higher Education

Although the Philippine government has enacted several policies fostering for gender equality, their implementation continues to be contradictory. This is supported by the study of Alibudbud (2023) which emphasize that gender mainstreaming in higher education institutions is often confined to compliance-based activities, like organizing seminars, workshops, trainings, or celebrating Women's Month, instead of integrated it to the curriculum. Similarly, according to Ofreneo (2019), patriarchal norms remains influential to institutional priorities, preventing the presence of feminist and queer narratives in academic spaces.

These findings align with the experiences of teachers in the classroom who are facing challenges on how to integrate gender-related themes into a traditional course framework. The struggle that they experienced is not only about curricular but also include cultural aspect where they themselves must disrupt biased assumptions that affect teaching materials and learner's engagement. This situation supports Bautista and Aguilar's (2022) claim that gender-responsive pedagogy necessitates both institutional support and self-empowerment among educators.

Echoes of Expression

A Creative Folio

Volume I, Issue VI (October 2025), National Circulation

ISSN (Online) 3082-4397 ISSN (Print) 3082-5741

Published Online at www.lakbaydiwapublishing.com

Publisher: Lakbay-Diwa Publishing

DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937 / TIN 492-741-614

lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com

Butuan City, Philippines

+639543906965

Pedagogical Transformation and the Role of Educators

Based on pedagogical perspective, educators are vital to realizing gender-responsive education. Incorporating gender-sensitive viewpoint includes rethinking aside from what is taught but how it is taught. A gender-sensitive teacher recognizes the interconnection of social and personal experiences of learners, fosters open dialogue, and values diversity. This supports with Freire's (1970) notion of co-learning in which both educators and learners involve in common thinking to challenge dominant social structures.

In actual practice, the integration of gender into the curriculum requires revising the course syllabi and diversifying instructional materials. It also involves crafting assignments that assess gender relative to each learner's field. For example, discussions of gender and leadership in management courses can enlighten how a particular organizational structure reflect social disparities. As Roces (2021) emphasizes, gender education cultivates empowerment by allowing students to understand structural discrimination and to visualize balanced social dynamics.

Toward a Socially-Responsive Curriculum

A genuinely gender-inclusive education should incorporate GAD-related frameworks in all courses while encouraging critical reflection. Gender education must also incorporate in all elective courses across disciplines from arts and technology to engineering business. In this way, it promotes transformative learning in which learners internalize inclusivity as an ethical and professional values rather than topic of study.

Moreover, HEIs must establish programs and projects that includes gender sensitivity training for all educators and Gender and Development (GAD) offices. They must also implement inclusive policy frameworks. These initiatives cultivate what Bautista and Aguilar (2022) describe as a "gender-aware academic culture" in which inclusion is upheld as both pedagogical and administrative priority.

In the long term, gender-inclusive education supports to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal No. 5, which aims to strive gender fairness and the active participation of women and girls. Higher education institutions in the Philippines can emerge as leaders in inclusive and equitable learning if their educational frameworks aligned with local realities and international standards.

Conclusion

Gender-inclusive education in the Philippine higher education curriculum goes beyond mere compliance but it embodies both theoretical and ethical project that reshapes the ultimate purpose and practice of academic teaching and learning. Grounded in feminist and critical pedagogy, it challenges academic institutions, officials, educators, and learners to confront discriminations and celebrating differences. The classrooms thus transform into an avenue where hearts and minds awaken, and where equality, empathy, and justice come alive together. When education genuinely embraces gender equality, it empowers individuals and at the same time strengthens the very foundation of democratic fabric of society.

References

- Alibudbud, R. (2023). Gender mainstreaming in higher education institutions: Challenges and prospects in the Philippine context. *Asian Journal of Gender and Development*, 15(2), 45-59.
- Bautista, J., & Aguilar, M. (2022). Teaching gender sensitivity in Philippine universities: Pedagogical reflections and classroom practices. *Philippine Journal of Education*, 101(3), 24-38.
- Freire, P. (1970). *Pedagogy of the oppressed*. Continuum.
- Hooks, b. (1994). *Teaching to transgress: Education as the practice of freedom*. Routledge.
- Ofreneo, R. (2019). Gender and work in the Philippines: Moving beyond stereotypes. *Philippine Sociological Review*, 67(1), 88-104.
- Roces, M. (2021). Feminist advocacy and education reform in the Philippines. *Asian Studies Review*, 45(1), 37-54.
- United Nations. (1997). *Report of the Economic and Social Council for 1997*. United Nations.